

Training-The-Trainers

Guideline

**International Course: Outbreak Analysis
and Modeling in Public Health**

Epimodelac 2023
www.epimodelac.com

Bogotá

1

November- December 2023

Guideline Authorship

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Funding | This work is part of the TRACE-LAC project (Enhancing Tools for Response, Analytics and Control of Epidemics in Latin America and the Caribbean), funded by the International Development Research Center (IDRC), grant number: 109848-002.

Acknowledgements | We express our sincere gratitude to all who have contributed to this project. This includes the 2019, 2021, and 2023 course participants who helped develop materials and learning experiences, as well as the trainers who patiently learned, shared their knowledge, and communicated questions to improve the material. We also extend our thanks to the practical leaders and speakers who designed the practicals and shared their expertise, and to those involved in logistics, planning, coordination, research, and management at the universities and funding organizations.

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Introduction

Welcome. This is a guide for trainers of the **International Course: Outbreak Analysis and Modeling in Public Health, Bogotá 2023**. Our support team of trainers should use this material to guide our participants during the practicals of the event.

Training the Trainers Methods

Trainers for the course were selected from former participants who excelled in the course or displayed notable knowledge and skills and those who, although not accepted into the course, stand out for their knowledge and skills are invited. Once selected, the trainers receive comprehensive details about the course content and structure, along with the course materials. They then engage in virtual training sessions where they review the materials and solutions, and address any questions that arise from the course guide. These sessions aim to simulate the course experience for the trainers and pinpoint potential areas for improvement in the content or delivery.

During these virtual training sessions, trainers are encouraged to collaborate, with those who grasp the material explaining it to others. The training sessions also include providing instructions for upcoming sessions and guidelines for the trainers.

This approach ensures that participants receive support in both their technical and theoretical difficulties during the course. At least one trainer is assigned for every five participants to ensure continuous support. In addition, there are additional trainers to ensure that support is always available in case of unforeseen events. The main trainers lead the group and are always available to offer assistance, while the support trainers aid the main trainers and provide coverage for absences.

Through this method, participants receive constant support to resolve questions, overcome technical hurdles, assist struggling participants, motivate others to progress faster, and cultivate a collaborative and supportive environment. This strategy also helps strengthen the leadership skills of the trainers.

Virtual Component (asynchronous)

Before arriving at the in-person course, the 80 participants had already completed a **prior online** training course (between November 10th and December 4th) that included 10 hours of training in five units.

- **Unit 1.** History of Epidemics and Pandemics
- **Unit 2.** Introduction to Epidemic Theory
- **Unit 3.** Introduction to R and RStudio (includes Tidyverse)
- **Unit 4.** Visualization with ggplot2
- **Unit 5.** Reports with RMarkdown

Participants are assumed to have at least the knowledge covered in these units. The online course will also be available to trainers but is not mandatory.

Logistic

Schedule Availability

The following table shows the times when you, as a trainer, are committed to supporting us. However, on day 1 (Dec 4), you may attend all activities related to the course, including the online component and conferences.

REMEMBER: We prefer that you attend the activities in their entirety since this will give you more tools to support our participants. In addition, the **trainers** who will be with the groups from start to finish were called **main**; the other trainers will provide support according to emerging needs.

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Practicals Session Attendance:

Trainer	Team	Name	Dic5	Dic6	Dic7	Dic8
Main	1	Arelis Alexandra Coral Chaucanes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sivirep
support	1	Alberto Castillo	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Main	2	Carlos Alberto Hernández Londoño	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sivirep
support	2	Johan Manuel Calderón Rodríguez	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Main	3	David Santiago Quevedo Vega	Yes	Yes	Yes	Tutor
Main	4	Diana Marcela López Orozco	Yes	Yes	Yes	Serofoi
Main	5	Geraldine Sarai Gómez Millán	Yes	Yes	Yes	Tutor
Main	6	Gina Paola Polo Infante	Yes	Yes	Yes	Vacineff
Main	7	Jonathan Patricio Baldera	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Main	8	Juan Camilo Rojas Hernandez	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sivirep
Main	9	Juan Daniel Umaña Caro	Yes	Yes	Yes	Tutor
Main	10	Juan Felipe Montenegro Torres	No	Yes	Yes	Epico
Main	11	Julian Otero	Yes	No	Yes	Epico
support	11	Angélica María Arango Gutierrez	Yes	Yes	No	No
Main	12	Maria Camila Tavera Cifuentes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Epico
Main	13	Maria Fernanda Carreño	Yes	Yes	Yes	Serofoi
Main	14	Nicolás Torres Domínguez	Yes	Yes	Yes	Tutor
Main	15	Roberto Germán Mesías Larrea	Yes	Yes	Yes	Epico
Main	16	Santiago Loaiza Betancurt	Yes	Yes	Yes	Vacineff

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support		Erika Cantor	Yes	Yes	Yes	Vaccineff
support		Felipe Segundo Abril Bermúdez	Yes	Yes	Yes	Serofoi
support		Mariluz Trilleras Mota	Yes	Yes	Yes	Vaccineff
support		Willebaldo Mantilla Rios	Yes	Yes	Yes	Serofoi

Development of the sessions

All course sessions, both theoretical and practical, will be held in person. The total number of participants will be approximately 113: 80 participants, 15 coordinators + 25 trainers.

- Day 1: Opening and conferences on data analysis and public health.
- Days 2, 3 and 4: master conferences will be held in the morning and practicals in the afternoon related to the theme of the day according to the event's agenda.
- Day 5: an Epiverse TRACE-LAC Libraries Challenge will be held

During the practicals, we will divide the 80 participants into work groups of 5 to 10 people for 16 groups. Each group will have an assigned trainer who will support the participants with technical questions about the practicals. Ideally, the trainer will have the same group of students in all the practicals. In this space, we expect to have your availability 100%.

If you need help or have any concerns, you can rely on our coordinating team, tutors, any of our main trainers, or José M. Velasco-España, the general trainer.

Interaction with Participants

We hope your interaction with our participants and everyone attending the event is professional, proactive and friendly, so we invite you to read our [TRACE-LAC Project code of conduct](#).

We hope you will make continuous rounds and be available to answer questions or concerns. If you see a participant who looks confused or is behind in the activities, please let your coordinator know so that they can assign a support trainer to this person.

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Each participant and support staff member of the course will have an identification badge; however, it is important that the trainers introduce themselves to their students and allow the students to introduce themselves quickly. The maximum time for this activity will be 5 minutes. While doing this, it is important that you help us keep track of attendance. The document for this is in the trainers' material folder.

Training for trainers

For you to be able to support the different practicals that we will have during the event, we ask that you join us for the following training sessions:

'Data Analysis and Modeling' Practical

Trainers of Trainers: Nicolás Torres Domínguez, José M. Velasco España

Date	Time	Topic	Responsible	Connection link
Thursday, November 9	7pm to 9pm ▾	Epimodelac- Real-time outbreak analysis - Ebola practical	Nicolas Torres & José M. Velasco E.	Link Real-time outbreak analysis - Ebola
Tuesday, November 14	7pm to 9pm ▾	Epimodelac- Building a simple model for Zika practical	José M. Velasco España	Link Building a simple model for Zika practical
Thursday, November 16	7pm to 9pm ▾	Epimodelac- Challenges practicals (in groups)	Each group	

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Thursday, November 23	7pm to 9pm ▾	Epimodelac - Disease X practical	Nicolas Torres & Zulma Cucunubá	Link Disease X practical
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Epiverse-TRACE-LAC Package Challenges

Sivirep - Geraldine Gómez
 Vaccineff - David Santiago Quevedo
 Serofoi - Nicolas Torres
 EpiCo - Juan Daniel Umaña

Links to materials for trainers

Access to participants assigned: [List](#)
 Access to [Materials \(in Spanish\)](#)

Certificate

Upon concluding your role as a trainer, you will receive a certificate that validates your participation as a trainer. Additionally, if you attend more than 90% of the total sessions, you will also be awarded a certificate of participation in the course.

List of available practicals

Session	Date	Coordinators
Practical Day 2. Real-time outbreak analysis parts 1 and 2	Tuesday, December 5, 2023 2:15 PM - 5:15 PM (Bogotá)	<i>Pierre Nouvellet</i> <i>Charlie Whittaker</i> <i>Kelly Charniga</i>
Practical Day 3. Practical	Wednesday, December 6,	<i>Zulma Cucunubá</i>

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Building a simple model for Zika	2023 2:15 PM - 5:15 PM (Bogotá)	<i>Charlie Whittaker</i> <i>Juan M. Cordovéz</i> <i>Juan Daniel Umaña</i>
Practical Day 4 Disease X Parameters	Thursday, December 7, 2023 2:15 PM - 5:15 PM (Bogotá)	<i>Kelly Charniga</i> <i>Zulma Cucunubá</i>
Practical Day 5. Packages	Friday, December 8, 2023 8:15 AM - 12:15 PM (Bogotá)	<i>Sivirep - Geraldine Gómez</i> <i>Vacineff - David S. Quevedo</i> <i>Serofoi - Nicolás Torres</i> <i>EpiCo - Juan Daniel Umaña</i>

List of R Packages

R needs to be updated to version 4.0 or higher and RStudio 1.4 or higher
IMPORTANT: Install one by one to verify potential errors

Share the text or a .R file with the following lines

Day 2

```
if(!require("readxl")) install.packages("readxl")
if(!require("binom")) install.packages("binom")
if(!require("knitr")) install.packages("knitr")
if(!require("incidence")) install.packages("incidence")
if(!require("ggplot2")) install.packages("ggplot2")
if(!require("epicontacts")) install.packages("epicontacts")
if(!require("epitrix")) install.packages("epitrix")
if(!require("EpiEstim")) install.packages("EpiEstim")
```

Day 3

```
if(!require("deSolve")) install.packages("deSolve")
if(!require("ggplot2")) install.packages("ggplot2")
if(!require("cowplot")) install.packages("cowplot")
if(!require("dplyr")) install.packages("dplyr")
```

Day 4

Crucially, RStan will be required. To install it, it is first necessary to install and configure C++ Toolchain (instructions for [windows](#)/[mac](#)/[linux](#)). After having correctly configured C++ Toolchain, run:

```
install.packages("rstan", repos = "https://cloud.r-project.org/", dependencies = TRUE)
```

For more details, visit [this link](#). This package is not included in the Installation Script.

The rest of the dependencies can be installed by running these commands:

```
install.packages("dplyr")
install.packages("incidence")
install.packages("coarseDataTools")
install.packages("EpiEstim")
```

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```
install.packages("ggplot2")  
install.packages("loo")  
install.packages("patchwork")  
install.packages("parallel")
```

If you encounter problems installing the `data.table` package, go to this [link](#).

The `{epiestim}` package needs to be installed directly from GitHub. Use the `install_github()` function from the `{remotes}` package to do this:

```
if(!require("remotes")) install.packages("remotes")  
remotes::install_github("reconhub/epicontacts")  
)
```

Day 5

```
if(!require("pak")) install.packages("pak")  
pak::pak("epiverse-trace/sivirep")  
pak::pak("epiverse-trace/vaccineff")  
  
pak::pak("epiverse-trace/serofoi")  
if(!require("cowplot")) install.packages("cowplot")  
  
pak::pak("epiverse-trace/epiCo")  
if(!require("treemapify")) install.packages("treemapify")
```

Practical 1. Real-time outbreak analysis - Ebola

Please complete the practical and think about the answers to each question. Then, look at the answers.

Working Groups:

Group 1. Pierre Nouvellet (Support: David Santiago Quevedo)

Group 2. Kelly Carniga (Support: Geraldine Gómez)

Group 3. Charlie Wittaker (Support: Nicolás Torres)

This Practical will be developed on the computer in R from 2:25 to 4:05 pm. Its dynamic is a practical guide. Challenges are presented throughout the practical that must be solved by the participants, and at the end of the session the solution is shared.

AGENDA

1. Explanation of the practical (5 minutes)
2. Do practical (100 minutes practical)
3. Discussion 30 minutes
4. Break (25 mins starts at 4:05 pm)
5. Final discussion (60 mins 4:25 pm to 4:55 pm)

Access to the practical: [Practical 1. Real-time outbreak analysis - Ebola](#)

Recording (Spanish):

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17ERbUfXh9idvhJXK6-IHS5mug3ML5gBG?usp=sharing>

Basic Concepts

In this practical session, the following concepts will be developed:

- Transmission of infectious diseases from person to person

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- Effective reproduction number
- Lethality probability
- Serial interval
- Growth rate
- Incidence

Data Reading

- **directorio_casos**: case dataset.
- **contactos**: contact dataset.

In the contact dataset, all are infections, but in each one, it must be clear who is the *infector* (person who infects) and who is the *infected* (person infected). Infectors are also called primary cases (first-generation or index cases); the infected are the secondary cases.

In this exercise, there are no total contacts but only infected contacts. This is so that the individual reproduction number (R_i) can be calculated using the *infector-infected* pairs. Calculating more things, such as the secondary attack rate, would also require uninfected contacts, but in this practical, we do not have that exercise.

Calculate Case Fatality Rate (CFR)

- **Case Fatality Rate in cases**: proportion of reported cases that die from the infectious disease but are identified as cases.
- **Case Fatality Rate in infections**: proportion of cases (reported or unreported) that die from the infection.

Video CFR vs IFR: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QsJf06sJpZc&t=329s>

Configure Incidence Curve with incidence Package

- **Incidence**: Number of new cases (incident cases) in a given period (day, week, month). Usually delimited by dates (start of symptoms, for example).
- **Incidence Curve**: Descriptive graph, usually a histogram, that allows to see the frequency of incident cases per unit of time (day, week, month). It is also called an epidemic curve or *epicurve*.

Basic Concepts

Estimate Growth Rate and Doubling Time

- **Log-linear incidence model:** Linear regression model $\log(y) = b_0 + rt + \epsilon$ where y : incident cases; b_0 : intercept; r : coefficient or growth rate in the context of an epidemic; t : unit of time; ϵ : average error 0. The dependent variable (cases) has been transformed to the logarithmic scale to linearize the expected exponential growth at the beginning of an epidemic and generated in R with the [incidence](#) package.
- **Growth rate:** Average increase of the log of new or incident cases $\log(y)$ per unit of time. Estimated in a log-linear incidence model.
- **Doubling time:** The time it takes for the epidemic curve of the disease under surveillance to double the number of incident cases, according to its growth rate.

Generate Contact Network

- **Contact tracing:** Identify and track people at risk who have had contact with a known case, that is, who may have been infected.
- **Incubation period:** Time interval between the date of infection and the date of onset of symptoms.
- **Super-spreading:** Occurs for some types of infections when the individual reproduction number (R_i), that is, the number of secondary cases, is much greater than the average. For example, for COVID-19, if the average is 3, one can see cases in which it reaches much higher values and has even been described up to > 1000 . This is common in several types of viruses, such as coronaviruses. Usually, in these super-spreading situations, the index is only equivalent to 20% of the cases, but it can explain 80% of the total infections. In COVID-19, the most common super-spreading situations are infections in churches, bars, nightclubs, educational centers, hotels, etc., usually related to crowding in enclosed spaces. Paper that allows understanding the phenomenon in a real-life situation: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41591-020-1092-0>
- Additional information
 - [epicontacts](#) package

Estimation of Serial Interval

- **Serial interval:** The time interval between the onset of symptoms in primary and secondary cases. Also called serial interval.
- **Generational time:** The time interval between the date of infections in primary and secondary cases.

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Symptomatic transmission (incubation period \leq serial interval)

Pre-symptomatic transmission
(incubation period $>$ serial interval & serial interval $>$ 0)

Pre-symptomatic transmission
(incubation period $>$ serial interval & serial interval \leq 0)

Figure with definitions of incubation period and serial interval. Source:

https://ars.els-cdn.com/content/image/1-s2.0-S1201971220301193-qr2_lrg.jpg

Estimation of Transmissibility (Basic and Effective Reproduction Number)

- **Basic reproduction number** (R_0): Average number of secondary cases infected by the same case in a completely susceptible population.
- **Effective reproduction number** (R_t): Average number of secondary cases generated by an infected index case at time t .
- **Instantaneous reproduction number** (R_t^i): Average number of secondary cases generated by an infected case at time t .
- Additional information
 - [EpiEstim](#) package

Practical 1 Solutions:

Solution challenge 1:

```
numero_muertes <- sum(directorio_casos$desenlace %in% "Muerte")

numero_con_resultado_conocido <- sum(directorio_casos$desenlace %in% c("Muerte",
"Recuperacion"))

tasa_letalidad <- numero_muertes / numero_con_resultado_conocido

print(tasa_letalidad)

#Otra posible solución.

# numero_muertes <- directorio_casos %>%
#   filter(desenlace == "Muerte") %>%
#   tally()
#
# numero_con_resultado_conocido <- directorio_casos %>%
#   filter(desenlace %in% c("Muerte", "Recuperacion")) %>%
#   tally()
#
# tasa_letalidad <- numero_muertes$n / numero_con_resultado_conocido$n
```

Solution challenge 2:

```
tasa_letalidad_con_CI <- binom.confint(numero_muertes,
                                     numero_con_resultado_conocido, method = "exact") %>%
  kable(caption = "***tasa de letalidad con intervalos de confianza**")

tasa_letalidad_con_CI
```

Solution challenge 3:

```
incidencia_diaria <- incidence(directorio_casos$fecha_inicio_sintomas)

incidencia_diaria
```

Solution challenge 4:

```
incidencia_semanal <- incidence(directorio_casos$fecha_inicio_sintomas,
                               interval = 7,
                               last_date = max(directorio_casos$fecha_de_hospitalizacion,
                                                na.rm = TRUE))

incidencia_semanal
plot(incidencia_semanal, border = "black")
```

Solution challenge 5:

Written in the guide

Solution challenge 6:

```
ajuste_modelo_semanal <- incidence::fit(incidencia_semanal_truncada)
ajuste_modelo_semanal
```

Solution challenge 7:

```
ajuste_modelo_semanal_df <- as.data.frame(ajuste_modelo_semanal$info$pred) #Predicciones del
modelo

incidencia_semanal_truncada_df <- as.data.frame(incidencia_semanal_truncada)

ggplot() +
  geom_bar(data = incidencia_semanal_truncada_df, aes(x = dates, y = counts), #Histograma
  stat = "identity", fill = "grey", color = "black") +
  geom_ribbon(data = ajuste_modelo_semanal_df, aes(x = dates, ymin = lwr, ymax = upr), alpha
  = 0.2) + #Intervalo de confianza del ajuste
  geom_line(data = ajuste_modelo_semanal_df, aes(x = dates, y = fit), #Línea del ajuste
  color = "blue", size = 1) +
  scale_x_date(date_breaks = "1 week", date_labels = "%d-%b") + #Formato para los ejes
  xlab("Fecha") +
  ylab("Incidencia semanal") +
  theme_minimal()
```

Solution challenge 8:

```
# Estimación de la tasa de crecimiento diaria
tasa_crecimiento_diaria <- ajuste_modelo_semanal$info$r

cat("La tasa de crecimiento diaria es:", tasa_crecimiento_diaria, "\n")

# Intervalo de confianza de la tasa de crecimiento diaria
tasa_crecimiento_IC <- ajuste_modelo_semanal$info$r.conf

cat("Intervalo de confianza de la tasa de crecimiento diaria (95%):", tasa_crecimiento_IC,
"\n")
```

Solution challenge 9:

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```
# Estimación del tiempo de duplicación en días
tiempo_duplicacion_dias <- ajuste_modelo_semanal$info$doubling
cat("El tiempo de duplicación de la epidemia en días es:", tiempo_duplicacion_dias, "\n")

# Intervalo de confianza del tiempo de duplicación
tiempo_duplicacion_IC <- ajuste_modelo_semanal$info$doubling.conf
cat("Intervalo de confianza del tiempo de duplicación (95%):", tiempo_duplicacion_IC, "\n")
```


Practical 2. Building a simple model for Zika

This practical is done in two parts A and B.

Zika Practical Part A

Presented by:

- Zulma. Cucunubá
- Jose M. Velasco

This practical will be developed on paper from 11:00 to 12:30 m. Its dynamic is a conference-guide.

General Objective:

Learn the basic concepts of Vector-Borne Disease (VBD) modeling through the use of diagrams and mathematical formulas with emphasis on the functioning of the methods using as an example a basic model of infection by an arbovirus, the Zika virus.

Specific Objectives:

- Recognize how a dynamic model is built.
- Define and identify relevant parameters to model VBD epidemics.
- Define the concepts R_0 , R_t , and herd immunity.
- Define and diagram the interaction between the different compartments of the system taking into account the parameters.

Solutions:

Flow Diagram and Equations of the Compartmental Model

- **Flow diagram (without parameters)**

NOTE: This diagram can be shown to students initially so that they can analyze it and, together with the practical equations, try to put the parameters in the scheme. Students can do it by hand on a sheet and show the photo or share the screen.

- **Differential equations of the model**

$\frac{dS_h}{dt} = \alpha_h N_h - \beta_h \frac{I_v}{N_h} S_h - \mu_h S_h$ $\frac{dI_h}{dt} = \beta_h \frac{I_v}{N_h} S_h - (\gamma + \mu_h) I_h$ $\frac{dR_h}{dt} = \gamma I_h - \mu_h R_h$		$\frac{dS_v}{dt} = \alpha_v N_v - \beta_v \frac{I_h}{N_h} S_v - \mu_v S_v$ $\frac{dE_v}{dt} = \beta_v \frac{I_h}{N_h} S_v - (\delta + \mu_v) E_v$ $\frac{dI_v}{dt} = \delta E_v - \mu_v I_v$

- **Flow diagram (with parameters)**

NOTE: This diagram can be shown to students once they have analyzed the equations so that they can compare the scheme they made with this corrected one.

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The Parameters of the Zika Model

Parameters

Parámetro	Definición	Valor
L_v	Esperanza de vida de los mosquitos (en días)	10
L_h	Esperanza de vida de los humanos (en días)	50*365
P_{lh}	Periodo infeccioso en humanos (en días)	7
P_{lv}	Periodo infeccioso en vectores (en días)	6
PEI	Período de incubación extrínseco en mosquitos adultos (en días)	8.4
μ_{uv}	Tasa per capita de mortalidad del vector (1/ L_v)	$1/L_v$
μ_{uh}	Tasa per capita de mortalidad del hospedador (1/ L_h)	$1/L_h$
α_{uv}	Tasa per capita de natalidad del vector	μ_{uv}
α_{uh}	Tasa per capita de natalidad del hospedador	μ_{uh}
γ	Tasa de recuperación en humanos	$1/P_{lh}$
δ	Tasa de incubación extrínseca	$1/PEI$
p_h	Probabilidad de transmisión del vector al hospedador	0.7
p_v	Probabilidad de transmisión del hospedador al vector	0.7
N_h	Número de humanos	100 000
m	Densidad de mosquitos hembra por humano	2
N_v	Número de vectores	$m * N_h$
R_0	Número reproductivo básico	3
b	Tasa de picadura	
β_{th}	Coefficiente de transmisión del vector al hospedador	$p_h * b$
β_{tv}	Coefficiente de transmisión del hospedador al vector	$p_v * b$

$$R_0 = \frac{mb^2 p_h p_v \delta}{\mu_v (\mu_v + \delta) (\mu_h + \gamma)}$$

Zika practical Part B

Presented in three Groups:

Group 1. Charlie and team

Group 2. José M. Velasco and team

Group 3. Juan Daniel and team

This practical will be developed on computer in R from 2:20 to 3:35 pm. Its dynamic is practical-guide. Challenges are presented throughout the practical that must be solved by the participants, at the end of the time the solution is shared.

AGENDA

Instructions (5 mins)

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Development of Zika practical Part B (45 mins with trainer support)

Group code review (10 mins)

Results review (20 mins)

Break (25 mins starts at 3:35 pm)

Final discussion (60 mins 4:00 pm to 5:00 pm)

Do the practical located at [Compartmental Models of Zika](#)

Basic Concepts to Develop:

- *Herd immunity*: theoretical proportion of the population that needs to have protective immunity against infection for the outbreak or epidemic to cease.
- *Mosquito biology*: key characteristics of the mosquito that have an impact on the epidemic such as: average life, incubation period, infectious period, biting rate, susceptibility to insecticides, etc.
- *Natural history of infections in humans*: exposure, infection, disease, final outcome.
- Contact rate: number of potentially infectious contacts between humans and/or mosquitoes.
- *Density dependence*: characteristic of some infectious diseases in which one or more parameters are affected by the density of another parameter.
- *Models structured by immigration/death and by age*: compartmental models where compartments are explicitly included to define age groups or migration flows.

Solutions

Solution point 6. Parameters of the model

Parámetro	Definición	Valor
L_v	Esperanza de vida de los mosquitos (en días)	10
L_h	Esperanza de vida de los humanos (en días)	50*365
P_{lh}	Periodo infeccioso en humanos (en días)	7
P_{lv}	Periodo infeccioso en vectores (en días)	6
PEI	Período de incubación extrínseco en mosquitos adultos (en días)	8.4
m_{uv}	Tasa per capita de mortalidad del vector (1/ L_v)	$1/L_v$
m_{uh}	Tasa per capita de mortalidad del hospedador (1/ L_h)	$1/L_h$
α_{hv}	Tasa per capita de natalidad del vector	m_{uv}
α_{vh}	Tasa per capita de natalidad del hospedador	m_{uh}
γ	Tasa de recuperación en humanos	$1/P_{lh}$
δ	Tasa de incubación extrínseca	$1/PEI$
p_h	Probabilidad de transmisión del vector al hospedador	0.7
p_v	Probabilidad de transmisión del hospedador al vector	0.7
N_h	Número de humanos	100 000
m	Densidad de mosquitos hembra por humano	2
N_v	Número de vectores	$m * N_h$
R_0	Número reproductivo básico	3
b	Tasa de picadura	
β_{hv}	Coficiente de transmisión del vector al hospedador	$p_h * b$
β_{vh}	Coficiente de transmisión del hospedador al vector	$p_v * b$

$$R_0 = \frac{mb^2 p_h p_v \delta}{\mu_v (\mu_v + \delta) (\mu_h + \gamma)}$$

Solution point 9. Model in R

The code of the arbovmodel model should look like this, and should match the differential equations of the formulas.

```
with(as.list(params), # entorno local para evaluar derivados
{
  # Humanos
  dSh <- alphah * Nh - betah * (Iv/Nh) * Sh - muh * Sh
  dIh <- betah * (Iv/Nh) * Sh - (gamma + muh) * Ih
  dRh <- gamma * Ih - muh * Rh

  # vectores
  dSv <- alphav * Nv - betav * (Ih/Nh) * Sv - muv * Sv
  dEv <- betav * (Ih/Nh) * Sv - (delta + muv) * Ev
  dIv <- delta * Ev - muv * Iv

  dx <- c(dSh, dIh, dRh, dSv, dEv, dIv)
  list(dx)
}
```

Solution point 10. Solve the System: Initial Conditions of the Zika Model

The reason why the number of Susceptible humans at time 0 is equal to the total population is because no human has yet been infected.

The reason why $S_v = N_v - 1$ is because the number of susceptible vectors (S_v) must be subtracted from the mosquito that is already infected $I_v = 1$

```
# Condiciones iniciales del sistema
xstart<- c(Sh = Nh ,      # Número inicial de Sh en T0
          Ih = 0,        # Número inicial de Ih en T0
          Rh = 0,        # Número inicial de Rh en T0
          Sv = Nv-1,     # Número inicial de Sv en T0
          Ev = 0,        # Número inicial de Ev en T0
          Iv = 1)        # Número inicial de Iv en T0
# Resuelva las ecuaciones
out <- as.data.frame(ode(y      = xstart,      # Condiciones iniciales
                        times   = times,      # Tiempo
                        fun      = arbovmodel, # Modelo
                        parms    = params))    # Parámetros
...
```

Solution point 11. Results. Visualization week and year

Epiverse TRACELAC

```
# Cree las opciones de tiempo a mostrar  
out$years <- out$time / 365  
out$weeks <- out$time / 7
```

Epiverse TRACELAC

Solution point 11.6. Interventions

Fumigation:

Effect: Increases mortality in mosquitoes.

Parameter affected by the intervention: μ_v (mortality of mosquitoes)

New parameter: μ_{sp} mosquito mortality due to fumigation

Change in equations and diagram:

$$\frac{dS_v}{dt} = \alpha_v N_v - \beta_v \frac{I_h}{N_h} S_v - (\mu_v + \mu_{sp}) S_v$$

$$\frac{dE_v}{dt} = \beta_v \frac{I_h}{N_h} S_v - (\delta + \mu_v + \mu_{sp}) E_v$$

$$\frac{dI_v}{dt} = \delta E_v - (\mu_v + \mu_{sp}) I_v$$

Solution in R:

```
# Parámetros
muh <- 1/Lh # Tasa per capita de mortalidad del hospedador (1/Lh)
alphav <- 1/LV # Tasa per capita de natalidad del vector
alphah <- 1/Lh # Tasa per capita de natalidad del hospedador
gamma <- 1/Iph # Tasa de recuperación en humanos
delta <- 1/PEI # Tasa extrínseca de incubación
musp <- musp # Tasa per capita de mortalidad específica del vector (1/Lv)
```

Epiverse TRACELAC

Mosquito nets:

Effect: Reduces contact between humans and vectors

Parameter affected by the intervention: b (Biting rate)

New parameters: net (mosquito net effectiveness)

d (Proportional reduction of contacts between mosquito and human)

Change in the relevant equation and diagram:

Solution in R:

```
# Parámetros
muh <- 1/Lh # Tasa per capita de mortalidad del hospedador (1/Lh)
alphav <- 1/Lv # Tasa per capita de natalidad del vector
alphah <- 1/Lh # Tasa per capita de natalidad del hospedador
gamma <- 1/Iph # Tasa de recuperación en humanos
delta <- 1/EIP # Tasa de incubación extrínseca
net <- eficacia_mosquitero #eficacia de mosquitero
d <- (100 - net)/100 #Reducción proporcional de los contactos
#entre mosquito y humano
```

Epiverse TRACELAC

Vaccination:

Effect: Immunizes susceptible humans

Compartment affected by the intervention: S_h (Susceptible humans)

Compartment created by the intervention: V_h (Vaccinated humans)

New parameters: vc (Proportion of the population vaccinated daily)
 pvc (Percentage of population vaccinated daily)

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} = \alpha_h N_h - \beta_h \frac{I_v}{N_h} S_h - \mu_h S_h - vc S_h$$

$$\frac{dV_h}{dt} = vc S_h - \mu_h V_h$$

Solution in R:

```
# Parámetros
muh <- 1/Lh # Tasa per capita de mortalidad del hospedador (1/Lh)
alphav <- 1/Lv # Tasa per capita de natalidad del vector
alphah <- 1/Lh # Tasa per capita de natalidad del hospedador
gamma <- 1/Iph # Tasa de recuperación en humanos
delta <- 1/EIP # Tasa de incubación extrínseca
pvc <- pvc # Porcentaje de población vacunada diariamente
vc <- pvc/100 # Proporción de la población vacunada diariamente
```

Practical 3. Disease X

Please complete the practical and think about the answers to each question. Then see the answers.

Presented in two Groups:

Group 1. Kelly Charniga & Nicolás Torres & Santiago Loaiza (Lina Cristancho)

Group 2. Zulma Cucunubá & David Santiago Quevedo & José Velasco

This practical will be held on computers using R from 1:30 PM to 3:30 PM. The dynamic will be a practical-guide. Challenges will be presented throughout the practical that the participants must solve. At the end of the time, the solution will be shared.

Agenda

Part 1: Individual or group (60 minutes). From 1:30 PM to 2:30 PM

Points 1-6 (10 minutes) - Introduction (10 minutes + 2-minute pause)

Point 7 (25 minutes) - Incubation Period (20 minutes + 5-minute pause)

Point 8 (25 minutes) - Serial Interval (20 minutes + 5-minute pause)

Part 2: In 5 groups of 8 people (60 minutes). From 2:30 PM to 3:30 PM

Develop a contact tracing and isolation strategy, and prepare a maximum 10-minute presentation.

Break: 30 minutes. From 3:30 PM to 4:00 PM

Part 3: Discussion and presentations (45 minutes). From 4:00 PM to 4:45 PM

Complete the practical located at [Disease X](#).

Training recording:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17ERbUfXh9idvhJXK6-IHS5mug3ML5gBG?usp=sharing>

Basic Concepts:

This practical session will develop the following concepts:

- Epidemiological delay distributions
- Biases in epidemiological delays: Censorship, Right truncation, Dynamic bias (or epidemic phase bias)

GROUP 1.

Pause 1 Solution:

How many cases are there?

```
# Q1  
nrow(linelist)
```

```
## [1] 166
```

What proportion of cases are women?

```
# Q2  
table(linelist$sex)[2]/nrow(linelist)
```

```
##      M  
## 0.6144578
```

What is the age distribution of the cases?

```
#Q3  
summary(linelist$age)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.   Max.     
##  22.00  33.00   36.00  35.51  38.00  47.00
```

What type of exposure information is available?

Close contact, skin-to-skin.

```
#Q4  
table(linelist$exposure, exclude = F)[1]/nrow(linelist)
```

```
## Close, skin-to-skin contact  
##                0.6626506
```

Why do you think exposure information is missing in some cases? Discuss.

Fear of stigmatization.

Now draw the epidemic curve. In what part of the outbreak do you think we are (beginning, middle, end)?

At the beginning.

Describe the groups. Do you see any potential superspreading events (where one case transmits the pathogen to many other cases)?

Cases 25 and 113 have an $R > 3$.

Pause 2 Solution:

For how many cases do we have data for symptom onset and exposure dates?

Calculate the exposure windows. How many cases have only one exposure date?

```
ip$exposure_window <- as.numeric(ip$exposure_end - ip$exposure_start)
table(ip$exposure_window)
```

```
##
##  0  1  2
## 34 11  5
```

Are the R-hat values close to < 1.1 ?

Gamma distribution

Epiverse TRACELAC

```
print(fit$gamma, digits = 3, pars = c("par[1]", "par[2]"))
```

```
## Inference for Stan model: anon_model.  
## 4 chains, each with iter=3000; warmup=1000; thin=1;  
## post-warmup draws per chain=2000, total post-warmup draws=8000.  
##  
##           mean se_mean   sd 2.5% 25% 50% 75% 97.5% n_eff Rhat  
## par[1] 1.975  0.003 0.361 1.340 1.717 1.949 2.211 2.742 10755  1  
## par[2] 0.324  0.001 0.068 0.207 0.275 0.319 0.367 0.468 11163  1  
##  
## Samples were drawn using NUTS(diag_e) at Wed Nov 22 18:22:37 2023.  
## For each parameter, n_eff is a crude measure of effective sample size,  
## and Rhat is the potential scale reduction factor on split chains (at  
## convergence, Rhat=1).
```

Log-normal distribution

```
print(fit$lognormal, digits = 3, pars = c("par[1]", "par[2]"))
```

```
## Inference for Stan model: c6aece6be405f0991ed71af1901b826b.  
## 4 chains, each with iter=3000; warmup=1000; thin=1;  
## post-warmup draws per chain=2000, total post-warmup draws=8000.  
##  
##           mean se_mean   sd 2.5% 25% 50% 75% 97.5% n_eff Rhat  
## par[1] 1.529  0.001 0.115 1.304 1.451 1.528 1.606 1.754 10601  1  
## par[2] 0.803  0.001 0.084 0.660 0.744 0.797 0.855 0.985  8918  1  
##  
## Samples were drawn using NUTS(diag_e) at Thu Nov 23 12:51:16 2023.  
## For each parameter, n_eff is a crude measure of effective sample size,  
## and Rhat is the potential scale reduction factor on split chains (at  
## convergence, Rhat=1).
```

Weibull distribution

```
print(fit$weibull, digits = 3, pars = c("par[1]", "par[2]"))
```

```
## Inference for Stan model: d35ce4e4b78b193107f404dc40cbc8ef.  
## 4 chains, each with iter=3000; warmup=1000; thin=1;  
## post-warmup draws per chain=2000, total post-warmup draws=8000.  
##  
##           mean se_mean   sd 2.5% 25% 50% 75% 97.5% n_eff Rhat  
## par[1] 1.372  0.001 0.145 1.102 1.270 1.368 1.468 1.665 11070  1  
## par[2] 6.960  0.008 0.778 5.559 6.432 6.914 7.465 8.591 10374  1  
##  
## Samples were drawn using NUTS(diag_e) at Thu Nov 23 12:51:09 2023.  
## For each parameter, n_eff is a crude measure of effective sample size,  
## and Rhat is the potential scale reduction factor on split chains (at  
## convergence, Rhat=1).
```

Do the 4 MCMC chains generally overlap and stay around the same values (fuzzy caterpillars)?

Log-normal distribution

```
rstan::traceplot(fit$lognormal, pars = c("par[1]", "par[2]"))
```


Weibull distribution

```
rstan::traceplot(fit$weibull, pars = c("par[1]", "par[2]"))
```


Which is the best model?

7.1.3. Compute model comparison criteria

Let's compute the widely applicable information criterion (WAIC) and leave-one-out-information criterion (LOOIC) to compare model fits. The best fitting model is the model with the lowest WAIC or LOOIC. We will also summarize the distributions and make some plots.

Which model has the best fit?

```
# Compute WAIC for all three models
waic <- mapply(function(z) waic(extract_log_lik(z))$estimates[3,], fit)
waic
```

```
##           weibull      gamma lognormal
## Estimate 278.11557 276.14843 272.9041
## SE       11.92307  13.42853  13.8732
```

For each model, find these elements for the estimated incubation period in the previous result and write them below:

Mean and 95% credibility interval

```
res_means <- apply(means, 2, quantile,
colnames(res_means) <- colnames(waic)
res_means
```

```
##           weibull      gamma lognormal
## 2.5%    5.151964  5.054353  5.002920
## 50%     6.337195  6.114576  6.339179
## 97.5%   7.902366  7.536311  8.411159
```

Standard deviation and 95% credibility interval

```
res_sds <- apply(standard_deviations, 2
colnames(res_sds) <- colnames(waic)
res_sds
```

```
##           weibull      gamma lognormal
## 2.5%    3.700467  3.408624  3.977764
## 50%     4.662194  4.368742  5.922026
## 97.5%   6.327025  5.864578  10.113489
```

Percentiles (e.g., 2.5, 5, 25, 50, 75, 95, 97.5, 99)

Gamma distribution

Epiverse TRACELAC

```
# Gamma
cens_g_percentiles <- sapply(quantiles_to_report, function(p) quantile(qgamma(p = p, shape = pos$gamma[,1], rate = pos$gamma[,2]), probs = probs))
colnames(cens_g_percentiles) <- quantiles_to_report
print(cens_g_percentiles)
```

```
##          0.025    0.05     0.5    0.95    0.975    0.99
## 2.5%  0.3384874 0.577708 4.119598 11.84247 13.77393 16.25629
## 50%   0.7147845 1.055581 5.114399 14.64894 17.22380 20.54755
## 97.5% 1.1838746 1.609993 6.294281 18.80301 22.42376 27.18235
```

Log-normal distribution

```
# Log normal
cens_ln_percentiles <- sapply(quantiles_to_report, function(p) quantile(qlnorm(p = p, meanlog = pos$lognormal[,1], sdlog = pos$lognormal[,2]), probs = probs))
colnames(cens_ln_percentiles) <- quantiles_to_report
print(cens_ln_percentiles)
```

```
##          0.025    0.05     0.5    0.95    0.975    0.99
## 2.5%  0.6089193 0.8271572 3.667261 12.47162 15.46233 19.81833
## 50%   0.9727520 1.2503304 4.598263 16.98066 21.80485 29.18082
## 97.5% 1.3731980 1.7047432 5.802374 25.38650 34.36038 48.98636
```

Weibull distribution

```
# Report the median and 95% credible intervals for the quantiles of each distribution
quantiles_to_report <- c(0.025, 0.05, 0.5, 0.95, 0.975, 0.99)

# Weibull
cens_w_percentiles <- sapply(quantiles_to_report, function(p) quantile(qweibull(p = p, shape = pos$weibull[,1], scale = pos$weibull[,2]), probs = probs))
colnames(cens_w_percentiles) <- quantiles_to_report
print(cens_w_percentiles)
```

```
##          0.025    0.05     0.5    0.95    0.975    0.99
## 2.5%  0.2241456 0.4231455 4.105487 12.56941 14.51359 16.78929
## 50%   0.4710275 0.7888226 5.293635 15.37022 17.88626 21.03089
## 97.5% 0.8414230 1.2892020 6.616211 20.05848 23.88578 28.85104
```

The parameters of the fitted distributions (e.g., shape and scale for the gamma distribution)

Weibull: shape and scale

Gamma: shape and inverse scale (aka rate)

Log normal: mu and sigma

Is the fit of the distributions as expected?

Epiverse TRACELAC

Answer: All three models show a good visual fit. That is why in this case, with even greater emphasis, we must compare the fit using statistics such as goodness of fit.

Pause 3 Solution:

Are there any cases of negative serial interval in the data (e.g., the onset of symptoms in the secondary case occurred before the onset of symptoms in the primary case)?

Answer: No.

Report the mean serial interval, as well as the minimum and maximum.

```
contacts$diff <- as.numeric(contacts$secondary_onset_date - contacts$primary_onset_date)
summary(contacts$diff)
```

```
##      Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##  1.000  4.000   6.000   7.625 10.000  23.000
```

Plot the distribution of the serial interval.

```
hist(contacts$diff, xlab = "Serial interval (days)", breaks = 25, main = "", col = "pink")
```


Include the following when reporting the serial interval:

Mean and 95% credibility interval, Standard deviation and 95% credibility interval

Gamma distribution

	mean_mean	mean_l_ci	mean_u_ci	sd_mean	sd_l_ci	sd_u_ci
1	7.658723	6.65395	8.707372	4.386498	3.602425	5.481316

Log-Normal distribution

OUTPUT < >

```
mean_mean mean_l_ci mean_u_ci sd_mean sd_l_ci sd_u_ci
1 7.780719 6.692829 9.300588 5.189349 3.936678 7.289224
```

Weibull distribution

OUTPUT < >

```
mean_mean mean_l_ci mean_u_ci sd_mean sd_l_ci sd_u_ci
1 7.693916 6.677548 8.809715 4.463549 3.797158 5.456492
```

The parameters of the fitted distribution (e.g., shape and scale for the gamma distribution)

Gamma

OUTPUT < >

```
shape_mean shape_l_ci shape_u_ci scale_mean scale_l_ci scale_u_ci
1 3.104917 2.201138 4.136793 2.528536 1.831139 3.645062
```

Log-Normal

```
# Serial interval results
si_fit
```

```
## Coarse Data Model Parameter and Quantile Estimates:
##          est  CIlow CIhigh
## meanlog 1.867  1.724  2.015
## sdlog   0.609  0.511  0.726
```

Weibull

OUTPUT < >

```
shape_mean shape_l_ci shape_u_ci scale_mean scale_l_ci scale_u_ci
1 1.792317 1.50812 2.090071 8.638298 7.481234 9.943215
```

Which distributions have the lowest WAIC and LOOIC?

WAIC

```
# Print results  
compare_gamma[["waic"]]$estimates
```

##	Estimate	SE
## elpd_waic	-202.009546	7.0118463
## p_waic	1.936991	0.4409454
## waic	404.019093	14.0236925

```
compare_lnorm[["waic"]]$estimates
```

##	Estimate	SE
## elpd_waic	-202.215546	7.0178113
## p_waic	1.874728	0.4106866
## waic	404.431092	14.0356226

```
compare_weibull[["waic"]]$estimates
```

##	Estimate	SE
## elpd_waic	-203.941362	6.9020056
## p_waic	2.003623	0.6633186
## waic	407.882723	13.8040112

LOOIC

```
compare_gamma[["looic"]]$estimates
```

##	Estimate	SE
## elpd_loo	-202.015856	7.0144149
## p_loo	1.943301	0.4437589
## looic	404.031713	14.0288297

```
compare_lnorm[["looic"]]$estimates
```

##	Estimate	SE
## elpd_loo	-202.218954	7.0182826
## p_loo	1.878136	0.4114664
## looic	404.437909	14.0365651

```
compare_weibull[["looic"]]$estimates
```

##	Estimate	SE
## elpd_loo	-203.956018	6.9097884
## p_loo	2.008279	0.6725387
## looic	407.912036	13.8195768

Practical 4. Epiverse TRACE-LAC Challenge

On this day, participants must develop a challenge in which they use at least one Epiverse package.

The packages on which the challenge will be based are four: *serofoi*, *vaccineff*, *sivirep*, and *epiCO*. Below is a brief explanation and frequently asked questions for each package.

4.1. *serofoi* Package

serofoi is an R package to retrospectively estimate a given pathogen's force of infection (FoI) from population-based cross-sectional serological surveys disaggregated by age, using a Bayesian framework. The package provides a set of features to assess model fit, convergence, and visualization.

Package Objective:

The objective of **serofoi** is to facilitate the implementation of Bayesian models using *Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HCM)* algorithms, which are implemented in *Stan* with *Markov-chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)* sampling techniques.

Prior Preparation for Trainers:

- Installation of *rtools* (if not already installed)
- Installation of the package. Among the package's dependencies, which are installed along with it, is the *Rstan* package. The latter is crucial for running Bayesian models, as it provides an interface with the *Stan* statistical programming language.

Package Documentation:

<https://epiverse-trace.github.io/serofoi/>

- Practice using the package through *Get Started*.
- Familiarize yourself with the force of infection models by reading the article "*An introduction to Force-of-Infection (FoI) Models*."
- Read the contents and follow the instructions of the article "*Real-life use cases for serofoi*."

Frequently Asked Questions about using *serfoi*:

How do I read the *serfoi* output graph?

The most important output of *serfoi* corresponds to the graph seen below, which summarizes the model's statistics, seroprevalence, force of infection, and convergence (See figure).

What does it mean that this process uses a Bayesian framework?

It means that Bayes' theorem is applied to integrate data and prior knowledge into the analysis. In this framework, the observed data are used to calculate the **likelihood**, and this is combined with the **prior probability distribution**, which reflects previous knowledge or assumptions. The result is the **posterior distribution**, which represents an update of the initial beliefs with the new evidence provided by the data. This posterior distribution not only allows for estimating the model's parameters in a more informed way but also facilitates obtaining credibility intervals (CrI), which are ranges within which the parameters are

expected to be found with a certain probability. These intervals reflect the uncertainty inherent in the estimates and are fundamental to interpreting the results of the Bayesian analysis.

What does prior and upper prior mean?

In the context of serofoi, prior refers to the probability distribution we have for the force of infection, while upper prior refers to the probability distribution for one of its parameters. For example, in the following table, you can see that the **prior** of the tv-normal model is a normal distribution with two parameters (mean and standard deviation). In this case, the mean is lambda and the standard deviation is sigma. The **upper prior** is then the probability distribution for the sigma parameter.

Model Option	Probability of positive case at age a	Prior distribution	Upper priors
constant	$\sim \text{binom}(n(a, t), P(a, t))$	$\lambda \sim \text{uniform}(0, 2)$	
tv_normal	$\sim \text{binom}(n(a, t), P(a, t))$	$\lambda \sim \text{normal}(\lambda(t - 1), \sigma)$ $\lambda(t = 1) \sim \text{normal}(0, 1)$	$\sigma \sim \text{Cauchy}(0, 1)$
tv_normal_log	$\sim \text{binom}(n(a, t), P(a, t))$	$\lambda \sim \text{normal}(\log(\lambda(t - 1)), \sigma)$ $\lambda(t = 1) \sim \text{normal}(-6, 4)$	$\sigma \sim \text{Cauchy}(0, 1)$

What is the n_thin parameter of the $run_seromodel$ function for?

It is an integer that specifies the period for saving samples. By using it, it is possible to reduce the weight of the Stan objects.

4.2 Sivirep

sivirep is an R package that allows the generation of automated reports based on individualized case databases of [SIVIGILA](#), which corresponds to the official epidemiological surveillance system of Colombia.

Package Objective:

The objective of `sivirep` is to provide a set of tools to:

1. Download, preprocess and prepare SIVIGILA data for later analysis.
2. Generate automated epidemiological reports adaptable to the context.
3. Provide feedback on the surveillance system to the data source provider.

Prior Preparation for Monitors

- Installation of `rtools` (if you don't have it already)
- Installation of the package:

```
install.packages("pak")
pak::pak("epiverse-trace/sivirep")
```

Package documentation

<https://epiverse-trace.github.io/sivirep/>

- Familiarize yourself with **sivirep** by reviewing the description of the functions in the article "Index of functions"
- Follow the instructions in the article "First steps"

4.3 *Vaccineff*

vaccineff is an R package that offers tools for estimating vaccine effectiveness.

Package Objective:

vaccineff aims to facilitate the application of different vaccine effectiveness designs. The vaccine effectiveness study designs supported by the package are:

- Cohort study (implemented in version 0.01)
- Negative test (in design)
- Screening methods (future versions)

Prior Preparation for Monitors

- Installation of `rtools` (if you don't have it)
- Package installation:

```
if(!require("pak")) install.packages("pak")
```

```
pak::pak("epiverse-trace/vaccineff")
```

Package Documentation

<https://epiverse-trace.github.io/vaccineff/articles/vaccineff.html>

- Familiarize yourself with the different designs supported by the package and what information each one requires to be implemented.
- Run the test code for the cohort design presented in the "Get Started" article
Read the function descriptions in the "References" article.

4.4 *epiCo*

epiCo is an R package that offers tools for the analysis of demographic trends, spatio-temporal behavior, and characterization of outbreaks for vector-borne diseases in Colombia.

Package objective:

The objective of **epiCo** is to offer tools that can be used to complement the analyses presented in the epidemiological bulletins of the local Health Departments in Colombia. In particular, **epiCo** provides tools to:

- Identify demographic vulnerabilities, including risk assessment based on age, gender, occupation, and ethnicity.
- Facilitate the understanding of epidemiological profiles in regions of Colombia with respect to the onset of symptoms, duration, magnitude, and frequency of outbreaks.
- Strengthen the transparency of the methods used in the analysis of outbreaks.
- Perform correlation and regression analysis with local socioeconomic and climatic information.

Prior Preparation for Monitors

- Installation of rtools (if you don't have it)
- Installation of the package.

```
install.packages("remotes")  
remotes::install_github("epiverse-trace/epiCo")
```

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Package Documentation

<https://epiverse-trace.github.io/epiCo/>

- Familiarize yourself with the package by reading the article "epiCo 0.2"
- Explore the demographic module of the package by reading and running the code from the article "epiCo - Demographic module"
- Build an endemic channel by following the instructions in the article "Building an Endemic Channel with epiCo"
- Read the descriptions of the functions in the article "References".

Explore the spatio-temporal analysis functionalities offered by **epiCo** by following the instructions in the article "Spatiotemporal analyses with epiCo"